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Review Article

Review On: Food And Diet Brings Changes In Gene Expression

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ABSTRACT

The food is basic need of humans and this basic need causes the various changes in the human body. In many studies, correlations between nutrition knowledge and dietary behavior have failed to reach statistical significance, leading researchers to question the relevance of nutrition knowledge to food choice, and the value of nutrition education campaigns. This study used a well-validated nutrition knowledge measure to examine the link between knowledge and intake of fat, fruit, and vegetables. The objective of this study is to aware the society or people about the intake of food in human body. This review presents 4 lines of evidence supporting a role for proteins in the regulation of food intake and maintenance of healthy body weight. It is concluded that the amount of food consumed and the degree of short-term satiety are strongly influenced by the protein content and possibly the source of the protein. Although the evidence presented indicates that more research is necessary to establish the role of protein in the regulation of long-term food intake and body weight, this role is less obvious. New functional foods, food formulations, and dietary guidelines for reaching healthy body weights could result from this kind of study. Particularly for fruits and vegetables, it has been demonstrated that some degree of nutrition knowledge mediates the socio demographic difference in intake. This implies that knowledge plays a significant role in explaining variations in food consumption and highlights the importance of utilizing more advanced statistical tools to study correlations between knowledge and food intake.

INTRODUCTION

Food is any substance consumed to provide nutritional support and energy to an organism [1,2]. It can be raw, processed, or formulated and is consumed orally by animals for growth, health,

or pleasure. Food is mainly composed of water, lipids, protein and carbohydrate. Minerals (e.g., salts) and organic substances (e.g., vitamins) can also be found in food [3]. Plants, algae and some

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microorganisms use photosynthesis to make some of their own nutrients [4]. Water is found in many foods and has been defined as a food by itself [5]. Fat is the component with the highest energy density, or calories, followed by water and fibre [6]. These days, most buyers are well mindful of what makes up a solid and economical slim down. A sizeable extent of these shoppers are moreover curious about eating solid and feasible nourishments. To begin with of all, a few commitments point to a solid impact of social components. Koch et al. contend that appall related with feasible nourishment options such as consumable creepy crawlies and lab meat may be overcome by open presentation treatment. That's, formal educate, retailers and nourishment makers, supposition pioneers, and guardians and caretakers ought to alter social standards by expanding consumers exposure to these nourishments and in this way normalize them. In the event that now not seen as degenerate, consumable creepy crawlies and lab meat may diminish consumers nauseate reaction, in this manner expanding buy probability [7]. The relationship between nourishment and the three fundamental columns of maintainability (social, financial, and natural supportability) has always existed, but it is currently becoming more visible. Alongside increasing environmental degradation and the scarcity of natural resources, under nutrition in its different forms affects thousands of individuals worldwide, highlighting food inequalities in the most vulnerable populations. Making food decisions is a complicated process that takes into account how food is produced and consumed. Individuals' dietary patterns may impact the main domains of sustainability and Quality of life [8]. Some studies have indicated that dietary preferences and eating patterns have evolved in tandem with the alter of worldwide nourishment frameworks and nourishment supply, coming about in a move toward expanded admissions of unfortunate

nourishment [9]. The alter of worldwide nourishment supply chains impacts the nourishment situations [10]. maintainable sound diets are dietary designs that advance all measurements of individuals wellbeing and prosperity; have moo natural weight and affect; are open, reasonable, secure, and evenhanded; and are socially satisfactory [11].

Need of Food

The food is basic use of human that gives the energy to body for working and daily functioning. Food contains the macromolecules and micro molecules such as protein, carbohydrate, lipid, nutrients, vitamins, etc. Food and is regarded as the indispensable aspects, which leads to effective growth and development. The people having a place to different age bunches, categories and foundations ought to get the basic supplements, which are respected as pivotal in boosting the vitality levels. An suitable slim down contributes to solid advancement, sound maturing and more prominent strength against maladies. On other hand, need of basic supplements in one's slim down leads to wellbeing issues and ailments. There's an colossal potential to create unused items, wellbeing mediations and start of more exact dietary rules will lead to advancement in wellbeing conditions through nourishment. When the people perceive the meaning of this potential, they will be able to get it that it is vital for them to meet their dietary needs and necessities in an appropriate way. It is basic to create the nourishment preparing strategies to create the diets healthier.[12] The nourishment things which are wealthy in supplements have to be be expended, as they contribute in driving to solid development and improvement. Nourishment and sustenance are the ways through which the people get the vital vitality. As when one is examining or working on an craftsmanship or making use of advances and so forward, they require the essential vitality and this vitality is given by the fundamental

supplements. Supplements ought to be supplanted within the body with the unused supply on every day basis.[13] The imperative capacities of supplements are to advance great wellbeing and well-being and avoid the event of wellbeing issues and illnesses.[14]

MACRO AND MICRO MOLECULES

Every phrase begins with a slight hint about what they might be cruel. The word macro is derived from the Greek makros, which means enormous. In terms of nutrition, macros are typically expressed in gram, such as gram of protein or fat. Three categories are used by many macros-based diets to categories macronutrients:

Carbohydrates:

present in foods like breads, pastas, and natural goods; each gram of carbohydrates provides four calories.

Fats:

contain nine calories per gram and are present in foods like oils, nuts, and meats.

Protein:

present in foods with four calories per gram, such as tofu, eggs, and angle It should be noted that alcohol is categorised by some diets as a macronutrient with 7 calories per gram. However, some diets exclude alcohol because it has a remarkably low healthy value when compared to the other three categories. Micros are measurable quantities that are substantially smaller for subsistence. The word "micro" is derived from the Greek word "mikros," meaning "little." The majority of micronutrients are measured in milligrams or micrograms. There are parts of micronutrients within the nourishments you eat, particularly natural products and vegetables are ample in vitamins and minerals. Micronutrient illustrations incorporate, but aren't restricted to:

- Iron
- vitamin B-6
- vitamin B-12
- vitamins

- vitamin C
- vitamin E
- zinc

Most macronutrient nourishments contain diverse micronutrients. In any case, most individuals wouldn't utilize a micronutrient strategy to counting calories since it would be troublesome to degree and track.[15]

ORGANIC FOOD AND HUMAN HEALTH

Although few clinical and epidemiological research have been conducted to far, certain studies comparing organic with conventional food have reported reduced pesticide levels and increased nutritional value in organic crops. However, increased levels of several bioactive chemicals have been found in organic crops through dietary intervention and epidemiological research, which may be associated with a lower risk of long-term diseases, including cardiovascular and neurodegenerative diseases and certain cancers. This suggests that the intake of organic food may be beneficial.[16]

HOW FOOD DIET ALTER THE GENES

Nutritionists have long known that you are what you eat isn't fair an expression. Later thinks about recommend that what you eat influences you and now and then indeed your children and grandchildren. This winter Nest assembled regarded specialists in human and creature wellbeing to talk approximately long haul of nourishment science. One topic to develop was the epigenetic affect of eat less and way of life on individual wellbeing. Epigenetic is the ponder of how distinctive organic and environmental signals influence quality expression.. For example, epigenetic signals can cause changes in the number of methyl chemical groups associated with a quality, turning it on or off, without actually changing DNA. A persons eat less is an vital source of epigenetic signals, and researchers are presently examining how eating propensities alter quality expression in grown-ups and their

offspring.[17] Nutritional decisions have an impact on gene expression without altering the underlying DNA sequence. Epigenetic modifications can be attributed to three main mechanisms: histone modification, non-coding RNA, and DNA methylation. DNA methylation is the process of adding a chemical group, or "methyl group," to certain locations on DNA such that it prevents the body's proteins from "reading" that section of DNA and, in effect, turns the gene "off." De-methylation, on another hand, has the ability to eliminate a methyl group and activate a gene. Histone complex modification is the second main method by which epigenetic modifications can take place. Histone modifications lead to specific DNA strands becoming encircled. proteins known as histones, which hinders proteins' ability to "read" the gene and causes it to become "off" while it is encircled by a histone. Chemical groups may be added or removed from histones, making them more tightly or loosely packed, consequently turning gene expression on or off. The third main route through which epigenetic modifications can transpire is associated with an entity known as Non-. Both coding and non-coding RNA are made using instructions found in your DNA. While non-coding RNA competes with coding RNA to influence gene expression by disrupting coding sequences, coding RNA is essential for the synthesis of many proteins. Despite their seeming complexity, these three methods are fundamental

to the process of modifying gene expression without altering DNA structure. Our everyday dietary decisions have the ability to affect the process of gene expression and the creation of the proteins that genes encode, which is the focus of the field of epigenetics. [18]

NUTRITIONAL EPIGENETICS

Among the environmental epigenetic factors that have been investigated and understood the best is nutrition. Unfavourable prenatal dietary circumstances, postnatal health, and elevated risk of illness have all been linked. 1 The Dutch Famine Birth Cohort, which was created as a result of the Dutch Famine of 1944–1945, has been extensively used to study the effects of starvation during pregnancy and subsequent health and developmental outcomes, such as an increased risk of type II diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular disease, metabolic disorders, and decreased cognitive function in later life. [19, 20, 21] 7. Long-term changes in DNA methylation brought on by early nutrition have an impact on an individual's health and age-related disorders for the rest of their life [22, 23]. Nutrients can affect the availability of the substrate or the activity of epigenetic enzymes such as DNMT, HDAC, or HAT, either directly or indirectly, which is required for such reactions. Consequently, this alters the way important genes express themselves, affecting our general well-being and lifespan (reviews available at [24,25]).

Fig No 1:- Dietary factors alter individual and trans generational phenotypes by influencing gene

.Thus, nutrients and bioactive dietary ingredients have the ability to reversibly change the state of DNA methylation, histone modifications, and chromatin remodelling, which can change the expression of certain genes and have an effect on general health. Dietary patterns, certain nutrients and bioactive food components may have positive impacts and mitigate the negative effect of bad lifestyle choices like smoking or being around certain toxins [26, 27]. Nonetheless, the discipline of dietary epigenetics is very new. epigenetic, so little is now known about the precise impacts of bioactive food ingredients on epigenetic and how they relate to particular phenotypes. Understanding the epigenetic markers set off by bioactive food ingredients may help develop tailored nutritional therapies and improve our comprehension of how different nutrients or diets affect our bodies. For instance, a recent study found that the epigenetic signatures of fruit and juice, as determined by DNA Methylation marks,

are linked to separate immune regulatory pathways, indicating that the health advantages of the two are not the same. The initial stage of customized nutrition is recognizing these types of variations among foods. [28]

FUNCTIONAL FOOD AND GENE CHANGES

As previously mentioned, certain common foods have been identified as having significant epigenetic effects. These include purple grapes, cruciferous vegetables, and other foods high in polyphenols, such as berries, green tea, curcumin, and garlic. By including these foods in one's diet, one can induce favourable epigenetic modifications that reduce the risk and progression of chronic diseases. When eaten frequently, cruciferous vegetables like broccoli, kale, and Brussels sprouts can act as powerful epigenetic regulators by inhibiting enzymes linked to methylation and histone modification as well as regulating non-coding RNA. These compounds

include sulforaphane and indole-3-carbinol. This collection of vegetables has been investigated for its potential epigenetic impact on the anticipation of cancer and the digestive system in general. Berries and reddish grapes, which are high in polyphenols, have an anti-carcinogenic effect via altering epigenetic modifications that promote anti-tumor activity and reduce irritation in general. These foods include substances like gallic acid, resveratrol, and quercetin that have been shown to help flip epigenetic modifications linked to activating genes linked to cancer. The potent capabilities of these everyday items have been highlighted by the observation that even a feast consisting solely of coarsely ground garlic can influence epigenetic modifications across a few attributes linked to cancer and resilient health. [29, 30]

FOOD AND NUTRIENTS IMPROVES THE GENE EXPRESSION

You've likely listened the word genome the one of a kind set of qualities you acquire from your guardians. Well, the epigenome are chemical compounds that join to your DNA and choose which of your qualities are exchanged on or off. Your epigenome is additionally acquired, but not at all like your genome, which is set in stone, it's reversible. Nutrients in nourishment can affect quality expression, says Fit bit advisor Joan Salge Blake, Ed D, RDN, clinical relate teacher within the department of wellbeing sciences at Boston

College, which is nice news in the event that you were managed a intense hand of DNA. You not able to choose your family, says Salge blake, but you'll be able choose your diet. Of course, the inverse is additionally true make for the most part unfortunate nourishment choices and you'll eat your way debilitated. With that in intellect, underneath are the supplements that influence our epigenome where to discover them. Point to eat a assortment of these nourishments in balance whereas too developing other DNA-friendly propensities. Crushing in more levels, getting sufficient rest, keeping your intestine sound, finding time to think, are a few of the ways analysts accept can offer assistance quiet those disease-causing qualities. And when combined with epigenetics they can movever offer assistance constrain the impacts of your ancestors destitute choices, possibly affecting the wellbeing of your family future eras. Make living a sound way of life indeed more com pelling. [31] When the imbalance of dietary nutrients (zinc, foliate, vitamins, selenium, niacin, etc) occurs in body then causes the alteration of gene DNA methylation and that cause Decrease In Gene Expression Increase, In Gene Expression Decrease, In Gene Transcription Increase In DNA Disruption. That also cause the unwanted Cell growth, Tissu differentiation, Cancer, Aging, etc as shown in figure No 2 [38].

Fig No 2:- Imbalanced Dietary Nutrients Affect On Gene

PARAMETERS OR FACTORS OF FOOD

Time:- The time of food intake is a very important parameter or factor that affect the human body and its body environment. Fundamentally the body required the vitality which gives by nourishment admissions. In a day the three time we are eat the nourishment (i.e morning, evening and evening). In morning, Breakfast is all almost breaking the quick of a night without eating. It moreover sets the arrange for your nutrition for the complete day and gives you the vitality you would like to confront what the day will bring. Beginning the day on an purge tank can take off you feeling depleted and coming to for nourishments which will not be in your feast arrange by mid-morning. Arrange to eat breakfast inside an hour of waking. This way, your breakfast doesn't mix into a mid-morning nibble or touching taken after closely by lunch. Lunch ought to be almost four to five hours after breakfast. For example, if you ate breakfast

at 7 a.m., lunch from 11 a.m. to 12 p.m., and dinner at 7 p.m. If eating lunch till 2:00 pm on a given day isn't feasible for you plan a snack to be consumed in the interval between the two meals. Since they haven't eaten enough during the day, many people tend to overeat after supper. The evening timetable should be the same as the ones you've used in the past, with a minimum of four to five hours passing between lunch and dinner. It isn't always possible to have supper at 4 or 5 p.m., so some individuals will need to have a snack in between. [32]

Quantity:-

The quantity of food you should eat for breakfast can vary depending on your individual needs, goals, and preferences. However, a balanced food typically includes:

1. Protein:

About 15-30 grams. This could come from sources like eggs, yogurt, or lean meats.

2. Carbohydrates:

Around 30-60 grams. Opt for whole grains like oats or whole grain bread, fruits, or vegetables.

3. Healthy Fats:

Around 10-20 grams. This could come from nuts, seeds, avocado, or olive oil.[33] The see on nourishment culture is still exceptionally significant. She centers on the satvik nourishment. Rather than eating to live individuals are living to eat. She talks around the kind of nourishment one should eat to lead a satvik life. For her the nourishment ought to be straightforward which keeps your intellect and body in control. The eating of fiery and wealthy nourishment will lead to awkwardness in one's physical and mental wellbeing. So, she inquires us not to over-feed our bodies. "Reduce food, O brothers, reduce food. Food causes diseases to grow and spread. Food leads to sleep which further leads To darkness, ignorance and forgetfulness. Ignorance causing distortion Of desire, body, mind, sense, heart and gas, Brings one to birth. Therefore do not over feed your body."[34]

Environment :-

The environment in which you eat can significantly impact your food intake, digestion, and overall eating experience. Here are some factors to consider for creating a conducive environment for healthy eating:

1. Setting and Atmosphere-

Minimize Distractions: Eating in a calm, distraction-free environment can help you focus on your meal and recognize when you're full. Avoid intake of in front of the TV or while working. **Enjoyable Ambiance:** A pleasant and relaxing setting can enhance your eating experience. Consider soft lighting, a tidy table, and comfortable seating.

2. Social Context-

Eating with Others: Shared meals can encourage mindful eating and portion control, as well as provide social and emotional benefits. **Mindful Eating:** Pay attention to the flavors, textures, and

satisfaction of your food. Eating slowly and savoring each bite can improve digestion and help prevent overeating. [35]

Process of food eating:-

The scientific process of food eating involves several physiological and biochemical steps, from the moment food enters the mouth until it is digested and absorbed. Here's a detailed breakdown:

- **Chewing (Mastication):**

Food is mechanically broken down into smaller pieces by the teeth. Saliva, produced by salivary glands, starts to mix with the food, breaking down carbohydrates through the enzyme amylase.

- **Swallowing (Deglutition):**

The chewed food is formed into a bolus and moved to the back of the mouth. The swallowing process involves the coordination of the tongue, pharynx, and esophagus to push the bolus into the esophagus. [36]

Posture of eating:

Sitting up straight at a table is the best position for eating and drinking, Your feet should be on top, Your back should be straight, Your food should be in front of you. When it radiates from expounding eating and nourishment dissent, the whys and wherefores are numerous and changed. Something so loose that can be so fair missed when it hails from to fastidious eating, tallying the way you sit in their highchair or at the table. Appropriate putting and pose is an irreplaceable component in bolstering, especially in youthful children. It is especially required from a prosperity viewpoint. A culminate Indian pose permits the brilliant body and head course of action coordinating nourishment from the mouth into the throat and absent from the aviation route, turning away choking. Scanty situating will lead you to feel tired amid a mealtime, rising destitute eating aptitudes and involvement an intensified hazard of nourishment or liquid going down the windpipe as an elective of the esophagus. In the event that you

hone torment or uneasiness amid mealtimes, they may development negative affiliations and start to show fastidious eating conduct at mealtimes. Instep, certifying appropriate situating from the

streak, you begin your count calories will be acknowledged in serving you to progress positive nourishment affiliations and learning appropriate eating and mealtime behaviors. [37]

Fig no 3: Various Factors Of Food

Why Is Eating Posture So Important?

- Ensures resoluteness of the chest to help the head and permit legitimate breathing
- The made strides head control offers way better jaw solidness chief to tongue control and lip robustness
- Affords security and ease
- Endorses well mindfulness on the chore of eating
- Allows for a more advantageous hand to mouth harmonization
- Averts conclusion of nourishment and liquid into the airways
- Endorses assimilation
- Inspires explanation and fulfillment at mealtimes
- Confines fatigue

- Encourages receipt and trial of modern nourishments. [38]

MEDITERRANEAN DIET AND EPIGENETICS

In some places, a Mediterranean diet grows spontaneously and is deeply embedded in local customs. It is not only thought of as a healthy diet but also as a way of life. Eating a diet rich in plant-based foods, fresh produce, whole-grain or half-grain cereals, nuts (which are high in omega-3 fatty acids and low in added sugars, trans fats, and saturated fat), and other bioactive substances is the foundation of a healthy eating pattern. Omega-3 fatty acids, sterols, flavonoids, carotenoids, and glucosinolates are only a few examples of the bioactive and functional substances found in the foods listed in that have positive health impacts. Furthermore, compared to other culinary methods like frying, the cooking methods employed in this

dietary pattern preserve these beneficial chemicals better. This section focus on the effects that the primary foods have on health via epigenetic mechanisms. Research conducted on animal and cell models has demonstrated that substances found in the Brassicaceae family and its derivatives have positive health effects, including the prevention of cancer. Epigenetic markers, which function as regulators and inhibitors of the

expression factors seen in the majority of malignancies, mediate this protective impact. Glucosinolates have been shown to modify DNA methylation in a way that lowers the chance of acquiring specific chronic diseases. Additionally, cruciferous vegetables may have chemo preventive and health-promoting effects through processes involving non-coding RNAs.[39]

Fig No 4:- Mediterranean diet includes

CONCLUSION

The food is a basic need of living organisms. In that the over feed of food causes the various dangerous or long term chronic diseases. Like cancer, diabetics, obesity, hypertension, heart attack, etc. Also the over intake of bad and unhealthy food leads to various changes in our human body such as genetic alteration, organ damage, diseases, etc. additionally, hormonal alterations brought on by overeating and leads to hormonal imbalance that causes the reduce sleep, happiness, sexual problems, etc. The good or Healthy food intake reverse the unwanted genetic changes and treat the genetic disorders also improves the body. Food is use as medicine to the body so the body requires the nutritious, pretentious, or vitamins also the proper time,

quantity, process and posture of eating is very important..

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